

COOPERATION OF THE PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION WITH THE FAMILY IN PREPARING THE CHILD FOR SCHOOLING.

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***Annotation:** Despite the differences in approaches to learning, the parameters for which in currently assessing the readiness of the child for school. The prerequisites for successful schooling are the preparation of preschoolers for this. Readiness for learning is the formation of all mental processes, as well as the personality of a preschooler as a whole, at the level that is necessary for successful adaptation and learning in elementary school.*

***Key words:** upbringing, training, development, formation, socialization, preschool education, sources of preschool pedagogy, subject of preschool pedagogy, object of preschool pedagogy.*

***Аннотация:** Несмотря на различия в подходах к обучению, по-прежнему остаются неизменными те параметры, по которым в настоящее время оценивают степень готовности ребенка к школе. Предпосылками успешного обучения в школе является подготовка к этому дошкольников. Готовностью к обучению – это сформированность всех психических процессов, а также личности дошкольника в целом на том уровне, который необходим для успешной адаптации и обучения в начальной школе.*

***Ключевые слова:** обучение, воспитание, развитие, формирование, социализация, дошкольное образование, источники дошкольной педагогики, предмет дошкольной педагогики, объект дошкольной педагогики.*

Prerequisites for successful schooling is the preparation of preschoolers for this. Readiness for learning is the formation of all mental processes, as well as the personality of a preschooler as a whole, at the level that is necessary for successful adaptation and learning in elementary school.

Despite the differences in approaches to learning, the parameters by which the degree of a child's readiness for school is currently assessed remain unchanged.

A large number of various studies clearly show that in order to increase the efficiency of preparing children for school, it is necessary to overcome the distance that has arisen between parents and kindergarten. The task that has arisen can be achieved through the conscious, active inclusion of parents and teachers in the joint process of raising a child. Thus, during the period of preparing children for school, the relevance of integrating the educational tasks of the preschool educational institution and the family is especially aggravated. A large role is given to the motivation of learning.

For a long time there has been a debate about what plays the main role in the development of a child's personality: the family or social education. Public education here refers to various educational institutions, for example: a kindergarten, a school. The opinions of teachers dealing with this topic are ambiguous. Some teachers spoke in favor of the family, while others highlighted public institutions. So, the humanist teacher I.G. Pestalozzi believed that "the family is a true organ of education, it teaches by deed, and the living word only complements and, falling on the soil plowed by life, it makes a completely different impression." The attitude of the child to learning at school, along with other psychological signs of readiness, forms the basis for the conclusion that the child is ready or not ready to go to school. Even if everything is in order with his cognitive processes, and he knows how to interact with other children and adults in joint activities, the child cannot be said to be completely ready for school. Lack of desire to study in the presence of two signs of psychological readiness - cognitive and communicative - allows you to accept a child

in school, provided that during the first few months of his stay at school, interest in learning will certainly appear.

Preparing for school is not an end in itself, but the result of organizing a full-fledged, emotionally rich life of a child that satisfies his interests and needs throughout preschool childhood, a unique age in which the foundations of future development are laid.

Preparing for schooling is a complex, multicomponent concept in which the following “layers” can be distinguished.

a) intellectual readiness implies that the child has a specific set of knowledge and ideas about the world around him, as well as the presence of prerequisites for the formation of educational activities.

Criteria of intellectual readiness for schooling:

- differentiated perception;
- analytical thinking (the ability to comprehend the main features and relationships between phenomena, the ability to reproduce a pattern);
- rational approach to activity (weakening of the role of fantasy);
- logical memorization;
- interest in knowledge, the process of obtaining it through additional efforts;
- mastering by ear colloquial speech and the ability to understand and use symbols;
- development of fine hand movements and hand-eye coordination.

b) socio-psychological readiness includes the formation of qualities in children, thanks to which they could communicate with other children and the teacher.

The concept of "preparation for school" is considered as a complex, as well as a fairly long process of preschool education of a child, which is distinguished by its systematic nature in a kindergarten or family. If we consider the components of a child's readiness for school, then we can say that it includes the formation of prerequisites for learning activities, such as the child's ability to act according to a

system of certain rules in work, listen to and follow the instructions of an adult, perform a task according to the model. Motivational (personal) readiness is determined by the fact that children have a desire to learn. Most parents will almost immediately answer that their children want to go to school, and therefore they have a motivational readiness. However, this is not quite true. First of all, the desire to go to school and the desire to learn differ significantly from each other.

A child may want to go to school because all his peers will go there, because he heard at home that getting into this gymnasium is very important and honorable, and finally, because by school he will receive a new beautiful satchel, a pencil case and other gifts. In addition, everything new attracts children, and at school almost everything - both classes, and the teacher, and systematic classes are new. However, this does not mean that children have realized the importance of studying and are ready to work diligently. They just realized that the status of a schoolchild is much more important and honorable than that of a preschooler who goes to kindergarten and sits at home with his mother.

Children at the age of 6 are already well aware that you can refuse to buy a doll or a toy car, but you cannot help but buy a pen or notebooks, since buying, for example, "Barbie" is dictated only by your kind attitude towards the child, and a satchel or textbook is a duty in front of him.

In the same way, children see that adults can interrupt their most interesting game, but do not interfere with older brothers or sisters when they stay up at home. Therefore, the child strives to go to school, because he wants to be an adult, to have certain rights. For example, for a satchel or notebooks, as well as the duties assigned to him - for example, getting up early, preparing lessons (which provide him with a new status place and privileges in the family). Although he still does not fully realize that in order to prepare a lesson he will have to sacrifice, for example, a game or a walk, but in principle he knows and accepts the fact that lessons need to be done.

It is this desire to become a schoolboy, to follow the rules of schoolchildren's behavior and to have his rights and obligations that make up the "internal position of a schoolchild", which is the basis of readiness for school. Of course, this position is formed in almost all children by the age of 7. However, if a child often hears conversations in the house that school is not interesting, that this is just a waste of time and effort, if he sees that the attitude towards him and his family activities does not change from the fact that he goes to school, then such a position may not be formed at all.

It is also important to tell children about what exactly it means to be a schoolboy, why he becomes more mature when he enters school and what duties he will perform there. Using available examples, already 5-year-old children can show the importance of lessons, grades, and school routine. All this contributes to the formation of a child's motivational readiness for school. Motivational readiness to study at school develops gradually. The first stage is precisely the interest in the external side of learning, in the learning process, that is, in going to school, in school supplies, in the rules of behavior at school. Of course, such interest is short-lived and it quickly disappears within 2-3 months. It is then that interest should arise in the content of classes, in obtaining new knowledge, that is, in fact, cognitive motivation.

However, this already depends on how and what the child will learn at school. The internal position of the student, that is, the desire to go to school and the willingness to comply with school duties and rules, is the main component, the basis of psychological readiness for school, the basis for the fact that the child will feel comfortable in a new environment. Without such readiness, no matter how well the child can read and write, he will not be able to study well, since the school environment, the rules of conduct will be a burden to him, he will try to get out of this unpleasant situation at any cost. This may be a distraction, a retreat into one's

dreams, it may be a desire to play during breaks, or a negative attitude towards comrades or a teacher. One way or another, such a state will be "interfere" with the child to study, no matter how well he was prepared for classes at home. Thus, personal-motivational readiness is no less important than intellectual readiness.

Kindergarten teachers are encouraged to carry out a number of activities, which, as a rule, include consultations for parents, drawer folders, parent-teacher meetings. The topics of these parent meetings and consultations are quite diverse, but they necessarily include information about working with parents in the process of preparing children for school, which in turn can provide them with pedagogical and psychological assistance. The successful formation of these qualities is reflected in a steady desire to acquire knowledge and skills, to make a sufficient amount of effort for this. Work with parents is carried out in several standard areas: the provision by employees of the preschool educational institution of the necessary assistance to the family in matters of raising a child; inclusion of all family members in the educational process; cultural and educational work with parents; joint work with parents to create conditions for the realization of the creative potential of the child.

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